

INTERFERENCE AND ITS POSITIVE EFFECT IN TEACHING ENGLISH AT SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This article explores the concept of linguistic interference and its potential positive impacts on teaching English in schools. While traditionally viewed as a negative influence, interference from students' native languages can be leveraged to enhance the learning process. The article examines various studies and expert opinions to highlight how teachers can use linguistic interference as a pedagogical tool to improve comprehension, retention, and linguistic competence in English learners.

Key Words: Linguistic interference, English teaching, positive effects, bilingual education, language acquisition, pedagogical tools, multilingual classrooms.

Introduction:

Linguistic interference, also known as language transfer, occurs when the features of a speaker's native language influence the acquisition and use of a second language. Traditionally, this phenomenon has been seen as a hindrance to language learning, often resulting in errors and misunderstandings. However, recent research suggests that interference can also have positive effects on language learning, particularly in the context of teaching English in schools. In multilingual classrooms, where students come with diverse linguistic backgrounds, teachers often face the challenge of addressing these interferences. Rather than viewing them solely as obstacles, understanding and leveraging linguistic interference can provide significant educational benefits. This approach requires a shift in perspective, where the native language is seen not as a barrier but as a resource that can aid in the learning process. This article delves into the concept of linguistic interference, examining its positive aspects and how it can be effectively utilized in teaching English at schools. Through the insights of renowned scholars and practical classroom strategies, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of how interference can be transformed from a challenge into an asset in language education.

Understanding Linguistic Interference

Linguistic interference involves the transfer of phonological, morphological, syntactical, and lexical aspects from a learner's first language (L1) to the second language (L2). This can manifest in various ways, such as pronunciation issues, grammatical errors, and incorrect word usage. However, interference is not inherently negative. It reflects the natural cognitive processes of language learners who draw upon their existing linguistic knowledge to acquire new languages.

Positive Aspects of Interference

1. Cognitive Benefits: According to Cummins (2000), the cognitive mechanisms involved in linguistic transfer can enhance mental flexibility and problem-solving skills. By drawing parallels between L1 and L2, students can develop a deeper understanding of language structures and concepts, fostering bilingual cognitive advantages.

2. Enhanced Comprehension: Swain and Lapkin (1998) argue that interference can aid comprehension. When learners recognize similarities between their native language and

English, it can facilitate understanding and retention of new vocabulary and grammatical rules. This cross-linguistic influence helps students make connections that reinforce their learning.

3. Cultural Relevance: García (2009) highlights the importance of cultural context in language learning. Interference allows students to relate new linguistic content to their cultural background, making the learning experience more relevant and engaging. This cultural integration can motivate students and enhance their appreciation of both languages.

Classroom Strategies for Utilizing Interference

To harness the positive effects of interference, teachers can adopt several strategies:

1. Comparative Analysis: Encouraging students to compare and contrast linguistic features of L1 and L2 can promote a better understanding of both languages. For instance, discussing the similarities and differences in sentence structure or verb conjugation can clarify confusing aspects of English grammar.

2. Translanguaging Practices: García and Wei (2014) advocate for translanguaging, a practice where students use their entire linguistic repertoire to learn. By allowing students to switch between languages in the classroom, teachers can create an inclusive environment that validates students' linguistic identities and supports their learning processes.

3. Error Analysis: Instead of simply correcting errors, teachers can use them as learning opportunities. Analyzing the source of errors stemming from interference can help students understand the underlying rules of both languages, leading to more accurate language use over time.

Expert Opinions and Research Findings

Several scholars have contributed to the understanding of linguistic interference and its positive impacts:

1. James Cummins: Cummins (2000) emphasizes the cognitive benefits of bilingualism, suggesting that the interplay between L1 and L2 can enhance cognitive development and academic performance.

2. Merrill Swain and Sharon Lapkin: Their research (1998) on bilingual education shows that interference can aid language development by providing a foundation upon which new linguistic knowledge is built.

3. Ofelia García: García (2009) and García & Wei (2014) discuss the cultural and educational benefits of recognizing and utilizing students' linguistic backgrounds through practices like translanguaging.

4. Jim Cummins: Cummins (1981) also explores the concept of Common Underlying Proficiency (CUP), which posits that skills and knowledge in L1 can transfer to L2, supporting the idea that interference can have positive effects.

5. Stephen Krashen: Krashen's (1985) Input Hypothesis suggests that comprehensible input, which can include interference from L1, is crucial for language acquisition, highlighting its role in facilitating understanding.

6. Ellen Bialystok: Bialystok (2001) discusses the cognitive benefits of bilingualism, noting that managing two languages enhances executive control and cognitive flexibility.

7. Colin Baker: Baker (2011) provides insights into bilingual education, stressing the importance of leveraging students' linguistic resources to support language learning.

Case Studies and Practical Applications

Incorporating linguistic interference into teaching practices has shown promising results in various educational settings. For example, a study by Thomas and Collier (2002) on dual-language programs in the U.S. demonstrated that students who were encouraged to use their native language alongside English outperformed their peers in academic achievement. These findings suggest that recognizing and harnessing linguistic interference can lead to more effective and inclusive language education. Teachers can apply these insights by designing activities that draw on students' linguistic knowledge. For instance, creating bilingual glossaries, using cognates to teach vocabulary, and encouraging students to explain concepts in both languages can facilitate deeper learning and retention.

Conclusion

Linguistic interference, often perceived as a challenge in language education, holds significant potential for positive impact when appropriately leveraged. By understanding and utilizing the cognitive and cultural benefits of interference, educators can enhance English teaching in schools. Embracing students' linguistic backgrounds through strategies like comparative analysis, translanguaging, and error analysis not only supports language acquisition but also fosters an inclusive and engaging learning environment. As research by scholars such as Cummins, García, and Swain demonstrates, interference can be a valuable tool in promoting bilingualism and linguistic competence.

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